

Goat Liver Lipase : An Efficient Biocatalyst for Enantioselective Transesterification of Secondary Alcohols using Vinyl Acetate as Acyl Donor

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Lipase from fresh goat liver has been shown to catalyze enantioselective transesterification of secondary alcohols in hexane using vinyl acetate as acyl source. In most of the cases transesterification takes place with alcohols of *R*-configuration, whereas in the case of cholesterol only the natural isomer (*3S*) is acylated with >99% ee.

In recent years lipase-catalyzed transesterification of alcohols with different acyl donors has been extensively studied for resolution of alcohols¹. This is because of the fact that lipases isolated from a variety of sources are relatively inexpensive, can function in both organic and aqueous solution, are simple to use and exhibit high degree of enantioselectivity for a variety of substrates. However, due to considerable differences in substrate specificity exhibited by different lipases², it is desirable to reveal the substrate specificity for each lipase. Various groups have also studied the effect of different acyl donors on the reactivity of enzymes³⁻⁵ to overcome the inactivating effect of acetaldehyde liberated *in situ* from vinyl acetate during transesterification process. In continuation of our interest on the use of nitroaliphatics as useful building blocks for natural product synthesis⁶⁻⁸, we were in need of an effective biocatalyst for preparation of nitroalcohols of (*R*)-configuration to be used as chiral bifunctional synthons and explored the crude lipase separated from readily available goat liver for this purpose using vinyl acetate as the acyl source. We report here the stereoselectivity of the enantioselective acylation of secondary alcohols mediated by goat liver (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Results and Discussion

Enantioselective transformation of several secondary alcohols of different structural features was carried out in hexane using lipase isolated from goat liver and using vinyl acetate at room temperature. The reaction was monitored by tlc and stopped after about 50% consumption of the starting materials by removing the lipase by filtration. Both the products and the unreacted alcohols were separated by chromatography. Enantiomeric excess of the unreacted alcohols were measured in the cases of known

alcohols by comparing the specific rotation with the reported ones and for the hitherto unknown ones by Mosher's method⁹ to the proton-nmr values of the corresponding MTPA esters. The enantiomeric excess of the new esterified alcohols were measured by first hydrolyzing the acetates to the corresponding alcohols and then by applying Mosher's method to the corresponding alcohols. Our results are summarized in Table 1.

It has been observed from Table 1 that in the case of alcohols 1-6, the faster reacting alcohol is the *R*-isomer. However, the reaction time needed for about 50% conversion in the case of aromatic alcohols 1-3 were relatively shorter than the aliphatic long-chain alcohols and in most of the cases the %ee of the esterified alcohols were excellent. When a 1 : 1 mixture of cholesterol and epicholesterol was treated with the crude lipase separated from goat liver as per procedure described under experimental, only cholesterol was transacetylated, although the time needed for 50% conversion was much longer. Excellent resolution of bifunctional nitroalcohols 5-nitro-2-pentanol (**5**) and 4-nitro-2-butanol (**6**), were achieved with 87 and 78% ee in the case of acetates *R*-(-)-**5b** and *R*-(-)-**6b** respectively. It may be mentioned that chiral nitroalcohols are important building blocks for construction of molecular framework of natural products through C-C bond formation reactions. Thus the present technique using crude lipase isolated from fresh goat liver as biocatalyst offers an excellent, inexpensive and simple method for resolution of a variety of secondary alcohols in aromatic, aliphatic, and steroidal series in presence of several other functional groups.

Experimental

Isolation of the enzyme : Fresh goat liver was cut into small pieces and washed thoroughly with distilled water. The washed liver pieces were dipped in distilled acetone and stirred vigorously with a mechanical stirrer fitted with a sharp steel blade for 4-5 h. On standing, the fine powdered liver settled down in the bottom of the container which was separated by filtration. The powder was washed sev-

eral times with acetone till the acetone become colourless. Finally the powder was dried under vacuum at room temperature and stored in fridge.

Transesterification of alcohols using crude goat liver lipase. Typical procedure : A solution of 1 (0.1g, 0.82 mmol) and vinyl acetate (0.37 ml, 5.0 mmol) in hexane (10 ml) was stirred at room temperature with dry powdered goat liver lipase (2 g) prepared as above. The reaction was monitored by tlc from time to time. When about half of the starting material was consumed, the reaction was stopped by filtering off the liver powder. After washing the solid with dichloromethane (3×10 ml), the combined organic phase was evaporated in a rotary evaporator and purified by pre-

parative tlc (1 : 10 ethyl acetate : petroleum ether) to give acetate *R*-(+)-1b and unesterified isomer of the alcohol *S*-(-)-1a in 49 and 20% yields respectively. Racemic alcohols 2-7 were also treated with the liver powder using the same procedure and the corresponding transacylated alcohols as well as the unreacted isomers were obtained (Table 1).

Determination of enantiomeric excess : The enantiomeric excess (ee) of the products were determined by 60 MHz ^1H nmr using Mosher's reagent⁹ and shift reagent. The racemic alcohol 4 (50 mg) and (-)-MTPA Cl (95 mg) were mixed with carbon tetrachloride (5 drops) and dry pyridine (5 drops) and allowed to stand in a stoppered flask for 12 h. Water (1 ml) was added and the reaction mixture

TABLE 1—TRANSESTERIFICATION OF SECONDARY ALCOHOLS CATALYZED BY LIPASE SEPARATED FROM GOAT LIVER

(±)-Alcohol	Reaction time (h)	Products					
		Alcohol	Yield (%)	% ee	Acetate/Alcohol	Yield (%)	% ee
 R = Ac, (<i>R</i>)-(+)-1b R = H, (<i>R</i>)-(+)-1a	49	98					
 (<i>R</i>)-(+)-2b	35	97					
 (<i>R</i>)-(+)-3b	37	99					
 R = Ac, (<i>R</i>)-(-)-4b R = H, (<i>R</i>)-(-)-4a	24	98					
 R = Ac, (<i>R</i>)-(-)-5b R = H, (<i>R</i>)-(-)-5a	40	87					
 R = Ac, (<i>R</i>)-(-)-6b R = H, (<i>R</i>)-(-)-6a	37	78					
 7b	92	>99					

(a) Cholesterol series

was transferred to a separatory funnel with ether (20 ml). The ether solution, after washing successively with dilute hydrochloric acid, saturated sodium carbonate solution and water, was dried (MgSO₄), filtered, evaporated, and the residue was purified by chromatography. MTPA-ester (20 mg) was added to an nmr tube and diluted with CDCl₃ (1 ml). Tris[3-(heptafluoropropylhydroxymethylene)-(+)-camphorato]europium(III) derivative [Eu(hfc)₃] was added until the methyl protons of its ester were well separated. Intregation of these peaks yielded a 1 : 1 ratio. Then compounds recovered from lipase catalyzed resolutions, were esterified with MTPA Cl and mixed with Eu(hfc)₃ as described and their enantiomeric excess were determined from the intensity of their methyl peaks. The acetylated products were hydrolyzed to alcohols with potassium carbonate in methanol and were treated similarly.

(S)-(-)-1a, [α]_D²⁵-32.4° (c 1.9, CHCl₃) [lit.¹⁰ [α]_D²⁰-36.1° (c 2.96, MeOH)]. Hydrolysis of (R)-(+)-1b with potassium carbonate in methanol followed by silica gel chromatography gave (R)-(+)-1a, [α]_D²⁵+34.74° (c 1.6, CHCl₃) [lit.¹⁰ [α]_D²⁰+37° (MeOH)]. The ee values of (S)-(-)-1a and (R)-(+)-1a were determined by ¹H nmr as described above. (S)-(-)-2a, [α]_D²⁵-22.5° (c 1.8, CHCl₃) [lit.¹⁰ [α]_D²⁴-26.2° (MeOH)]; (R)-(+)-2b, [α]_D²⁵+91° (c 1.6, CHCl₃) [lit.¹⁰ [α]_D²⁴+114° (CHCl₃)]. The ee values of (S)-(-)-2a and (R)-(+)-2b were determined by ¹H nmr as described above. (S)-(-)-3a, [α]_D²⁵-45° (c, 1.6, CHCl₃) [lit.^{11a} [α]_D²⁴-54° (neat)]; (R)-(+)-3b, [α]_D²⁵+88.25° (c 2.6, CHCl₃). The ee values of (S)-(-)-3a and (R)-(+)-3b were determined by ¹H nmr as described above. (S)-(+)-4a, [α]_D²⁵+5.46° (c 0.93, CHCl₃), [lit.¹² [α]_D²⁰+7.96° (neat)]. Hydrolysis of (R)-(-)-4b with potassium carbonate in methanol followed by silica gel chromatography gave (R)-(-)-4a, [α]_D²⁵-6.05° (c 4.0, CHCl₃). The ee values of (S)-(+)-4a and (R)-(-)-4a were determined by ¹H nmr as described above. (S)-(+)-5a, [α]_D²⁵+11.1° (c 1.6, CHCl₃), [lit.¹³ [α]_D²⁰+16.0° (c, 1.96, CHCl₃)]. Hydrolysis of (R)-(-)-5b with potassium carbonate in methanol followed by silica gel chromatography gave (R)-(-)-5a, [α]_D²⁵-8.5° (c 0.53, CHCl₃) [lit.¹³ [α]_D²⁵-14.3° (CHCl₃)]. The ee values of (S)-(+)-5a and (R)-(-)-5a were determined by ¹H nmr as described above. 6-(S)-(+)-6a, [α]_D²⁵+34° (c 1.6, CHCl₃) [lit.¹³ [α]_D²⁰+40.4° (c 1.96, CHCl₃)]. Hydrolysis of (R)-(-)-6b with potassium carbonate in methanol followed by silica gel chromatography gave (R)-(-)-6a, [α]_D²⁵-13.5° (c 1.53, CHCl₃) [lit.¹³ [α]_D²⁰-16.2° (c 6.87)]. The ee values of (S)-(+)-5a and (R)-(-)-5a were determined by ¹H nmr as described above. 7- β -Cholesterol (0.5 g, 1.3 mmol) was oxidized with PCC (0.43 g, 2 mmol) in dry CH₂Cl₂ to afford cholest-5-ene-3-one (0.45 g, 1.2 mmol). Reduction of cholest-5-ene-3-one (0.4 g, 1 mmol) with NaBH₄ (0.06 g, 1.5 mmol) resulted a mixture of β -cholesterol (0.3 g) and epicholesterol (0.08 g). β -

Cholesterol (50 mg, 0.3 mmol) and epicholesterol (50 mg, 0.3 mmol) were mixed in a flask and treated with goat liver lipase (2 g) for 96 h and worked up as described in the general procedure. Yield : epicholesterol, 48 mg (96%) and β -cholesterol, 46 mg (92%).

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